

OHEJP SimEx

Handbook for

NEL and LEL

SimEx is an OHEJP commissioned tabletop exercise designed to facilitate a cross-sector dialogue regarding outbreak management with a One Health perspective. The focus is on cross-sector cooperation, communication, and information sharing. It also incorporates tools and results from other OHEJP projects.

This document contains general information regarding the exercise and recommendations for preparing.

Responsible partner: SVA

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Introduction

The main purpose of the exercise is to increase the understanding of the benefits of a One Health perspective, and we try to make this a learning and developing experience, with some possibility to identify gaps and needs. It is in other words not a testing exercise.

Our hope and aim is that after the conduction the training audience has:

- A better knowledge about the other sectors and an increased understanding regarding their different assignments and needs.
- Increased knowledge about benefits of harmonized data and identified difficulties regarding data sharing.
- A better ability to communicate across sectors and identify difficulties.
- Has had some opportunity to get to know more about OHEJP and some of the outcomes.

The scenario is divided into three parts. This is an artificial separation to make it easier for you to know what objectives to focus on and to organise the conduction.

1. OHEJP related information

The SimEx is an exercise designed and conducted under task 4.6 starting Y4 (2021) of OHEJP Work Package (WP) 4; Joint Integrative Projects, which aims to develop joint resources (infrastructure and work processes) across the three domains of the OHEJP (foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats) through capacity building within the disciplines defined by the Integrative Strategy Matrix.

The SimEx runs M37-60 and is finally reported in deliverable D4.30 “*Report on the OHEJP exercise (SimEx)*” in M63.

The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

The project’s directive is validated by the OHEJP Programme Management Team (PMT), and the final version is approved by the SimEx Steering Board.

The exercise has been prepared by an Exercise Planning Team, coordinated by staff from the National Veterinary Agency in Sweden (SVA).

2. Project organisation

3. Acknowledgement

This work was supported by funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830: One Health European Joint Programme.

About the exercise

1. Aims and objectives

1.1. Overall aim

To practice the One Health capability, capacity, and interoperability of authorities in Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety to work together.

1.2. Objectives - OHEJP level

1.2.1. *Sharing of outbreak data*

The participants shall gain an increased understanding on the importance of creating harmonized databases and data sharing.

1.2.2. *Communication in an outbreak situation (laboratory results, risk assessment)*

- Following the exercise, participants shall have gained an increased understanding of a One Health perspective during a zoonotic outbreak.
- Following the exercise, participants shall have better knowledge of how to use guidelines, tools, and practices available, with focus on those developed within the OHEJP project.
- Following the exercise, participants shall have gained improved insight into creating a common situation picture.
- Following the exercise, participants shall have gained a better understanding of how to create common main messages and identify different perspectives.

1.2.3. *Role and functionality of currently available systems*

- Following the exercise, participants shall have improved their knowledge of how and when collaboration takes place at national, regional, and local level in the event of a zoonotic outbreak.
- Following the exercise, participants shall have a better understanding of their and other actors' roles and responsibilities during a zoonotic outbreak.

1.3. Objectives - National level

To be defined separately per country.

2. Exercise Format

SimEx is a table top exercise to be conducted at national level by the applying institutes. Conduction will take place between May and July 2022, at dates decided by each participating nation individually. It is intended to run for approx. 2 days, but may be altered by the participating nations individually.

The exercise will focus on an outbreak, and consists of three parts, each connected to one of the main objectives. The simulated period covers early detection, tracing, assessment, and communication.

- Exercise document -

The exercise is structured into a number of injects, presented on a master events list, which is designed to create situations, provide specific data and keep the scenario on track and moving forward. Injects consist of one instructional page and one page to be given to participants as paper copies throughout the conduction.

For more information about tabletop exercises, please read the [ECDC Simulation Exercise Handbook](#).

Participating personnel

Exercise preparation and conduction requires a variety of personnel resources. Below is a short description of these.

1. Local Exercise Leader (LEL)

Each participating sector or institute needs one Local Exercise Leader. This role is based upon the 'exercise director/controller' role found within the ECDC Simulation Exercise handbook. We have mainly been using this handbook to plan the exercise.

Based on the guides and instructions provided by the SimEx Project Team, the Local Exercise Leader will plan and facilitate their own institution's participation.

The Local Exercise Leader should:

- Support the NEL.
- Be the link between SimEx Project Team and own institution.
- Be the link between NEL and own institution.
- Cooperate with Local Evaluator.
- Attend the workshop held in March. This will be 2–3 days of instructions and training to understand the scenario and exercise.
- Set up institutional objectives (optional).
- Identify persons and fill positions in the training audience.
- Prepare the training audience and personnel for the exercise.
- Lead the exercise and keep training audience on track.
- Make sure the training audience and exercise personnel have all necessary equipment.

2. National Exercise Leader (NEL)

Each participating country needs one National Exercise Leader. Ideally this person should also be one of the Local Exercise Leaders.

Based on the guides and instructions provided by the SimEx Project Team, the National Exercise Leader is supposed to lead and coordinate their own country's participation.

The National Exercise Leader should:

- Adapt the exercise for national routines and procedures.
- Coordinate Local Exercise Leaders.
- Set up national objectives (optional).
- Harmonize institute objectives (if any).

3. Local Evaluator

Each institute or sector should appoint a Local Evaluator. This person is responsible for the evaluation during and after the conduction. Together with other evaluators from their own country and the LEL, the Local Evaluator should create the final report. They must be able to determine if there is a need for a classified national report, and a public report to deliver to the SimEx Project Team.

The Local Evaluator should:

- Cooperate with LEL.
- Cooperate and coordinate with the other Local Evaluators from their own country.
- Translate the evaluation documents (if needed. Delivered in English).
- Monitor and evaluate, and facilitate the training audience's evaluation, during conduction.
- Compile results and write a report.

4. Training Audience

The training audience is identified and invited by the Local Exercise Leader for each institute. As the scenario is an outbreak of a food-borne zoonosis and focus is on increasing mutual understanding across sectors (Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety), identifying collaboration gaps, and finding new ways to cooperate, the training audience should consist of people that normally work in an outbreak related position. Below we suggest competences to be considered relevant for the conduction.

- Epidemiologists
- Veterinarian
- Laboratory personnel (all sectors) *
- Food-borne disease/medical expert
- Communications officer (all sectors) **
- Relevant authorities

* It is a dry exercise.

** Including one communications officer (per sector if possible) is recommended, although they would not need to join until the third part of the scenario (which will be conducted the second day).

N.B. If your organisation has a large experience from working across the three sectors, you could consider using this as an opportunity to introduce junior staff, or personnel working with outbreaks, but not normally part of the outbreak management team. This could then be a national and/or institutional objective.

4.1. Number of participants

For the conduction to be providing we recommend a minimum of 2 persons per sector (Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety). It is beneficial to have the same expertise from different sectors if possible, since this may add to the discussions. There is no maximum limit, but if there are more than 4 persons per sector, the logistical part may be more complicated.

4.2. Decisionmakers

There are several different legal systems within the participating countries. If you would require an authority or ministry to play an active role in a normal outbreak situation, it is recommended that you invite someone to represent them as well.

4.3. Missing sectors

For some countries, not all sectors are a part of the OHEJP. We strongly suggest that you invite representatives from the missing ones as a part of the training audience. Missing out on the parts where cross-sector cooperation is the primary focus will make the participation less rewarding.

Preparations

1. Scenario

The exercise is delivered to you as a word file, with parts for the LEL and parts for the training audience.

Since it is all delivered in English you may want to translate everything or parts.

The team has created a scenario with the aim to make it as general as possible, to suit all participating countries. Still there may be parts that won't feel adequate for you, such as food specifications and methods. If so, please feel free to change this. If you need support, please send an email to simex@sva.se.

2. Training audience

There is no need for a pre-training, but since the exercise is supposed to be a learning experience for all participants it is important that they are well acquainted with the procedures and functions of their own sectors and institutes.

3. Venue

Since each participating country has its own prerequisites regarding number of participants and costs, the choice of type and size of venue must be made at national level. However, we strongly encourage gathering at one single venue, since meeting in person is an important part of creating relations and trust. A conference room with enough space for the participants to gather around a table, but also to be able to re-group sector-wise for shorter periods (or adjacent rooms, if possible).

Since the training audience will use computers in some parts and may want to take notes, tables, Wi-fi and power sources may need to be considered.

If your training audience is less than 10 persons, gathering them around one table may be sufficient, but if more people will attend you may need to consider how to split them into two groups. If you have questions or need help to find a solution please let us know and we will be happy to help (simex@sva.se).

In order for the exercise to run smoothly, lunch as well as refreshments should be considered. It doesn't have to be on the institute's expense, but make sure there is enough time to reach restaurants or cafeterias nearby, and maybe make a reservation. Networking is an important part of the exercise, and some extra time to connect is just positive.

Please, remember that SimEx won't cover expenses or salaries related to the conduction.

Appendix A. Suggested plan for preparation and conduction

All hours are a rough estimate and may vary strongly depending on national and personal needs, level of engagement, available LELs to share tasks etc. Therefore, in some parts it is not even possible to estimate the time needed on a general level.

When it comes to the potentially co-funded time for LEL and NEL, the indicated months are a maximum that can be applied for in the budget. If the actual time spent is less, then you simply request less when reporting worked hours.

Please, remember that the decision whether to allocate money for co-funding will be done in late April 2022, and co-funding is only available for LEL/NEL, not for evaluators, training audience, venue, or other expenses.

Listed tasks are just on a general level, detailed tasks and information is provided over time.

1. 1st January-18th March 2022: 2-3 days

Tasks

- Read and respond to information from SimEx Project Team.
- Start coordinating within the country.
- Start considering training audience.
- Start considering suitable dates for conduction.

Additional for NEL: Coordinating the above.

2. 21st-23rd March 2022: 3 full days

Tasks

- Attending remote workshop including some preparation and travel day 1 and 3 (if travelling).

Additional for NEL: Arrange meeting at national level if possible.

3. Between March and your chosen date for conduction of exercise: not possible to estimate

Tasks

- Work with and adjust the scenario to make it suit national prerequisites and needs.
- Translate injects and evaluations (if needed).
- Recruit, coordinate and inform training audience.
- Consider adding national/local injects or objectives.
- Book venue and ensure it has required audio-visual capacity, can accommodate all players and has all other facilities required.

- Read and respond to information from the SimEx Project Team.

Additional for NEL: Coordinate the work and who does what. Keep a dialogue with the SimEx Project Team regarding issues.

4. Conduction: 2 days + time to prepare and break-up

Tasks

- Prepare the venue.
- Conduct exercise as facilitators and exercise leaders.
- Support the Local Evaluator(s).

Additional for NEL: Coordinate the above.

5. After conduction – September: not possible to estimate

Tasks

- Write a report on behalf of the institute, in cooperation with the Local Evaluator(s).

Additional for NEL: Gather institutes' reports and add national conclusions.

6. Rest of September – 31st December: 3-4 days

Tasks

- Read and comment on the SimEx final report.
- Attend remote presentation of results.
- Present relevant results to institute.